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Abstract

Wood is one of the key materials in archaeological research. Information about procedures, technology, economy and the environment are stored in both the shape of the object and in the structure of the wood. Wood is mainly preserved under waterlogged and anoxic conditions, and archaeological objects need conservation af-

INTRODUCTION

Wooden objects are rare in archaeological contexts and in temperate zones are mainly preserved in waterlogged and anoxic conditions. Since wood is an abundant material that can be easily worked, it has played a crucial role in the technological evolution of humankind. Thus, wooden objects hold essential information for archaeological research about the procedures, technology, economy and environment in the past. Additionally, wooden finds provide dendrochronological data that can help to date sites.

Dendrochronology is a widespread, reliable and very accurate method for dating archaeological wooden finds and, therefore, an essential tool for archaeological research. For conventional dendrochronological dating, the artefact must be cut or drilled, which is not feasible with many archaeological finds. Therefore, non-destructive dating methods are essential for studying artefacts in a responsible way for future generations. Computed tomography (CT) is an appropriate non-destructive technique for archaeological sciences (Stelzner 2020) that provides very promising information in the field of dendroarchaeology, including conservation science (see below).

Because of the vulnerability of waterlogged finds, conservation treatments must be initiated relatively rapidly. The principal aim of conservation is to bring an artefact into a condition of long-term chemical stability and to achieve a homogeneous stabilisation of the structure. However, in the case of archaeological wood, treatment may impact the future non-destructive dendrochronological analyses with CT.

In 2019, work began on the binational project CuTAWAY (Conservation and Wood Analyses) funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG – Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) and the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNF – Schweizerischen Nationalfonds). The aim of this project is to provide new insights into conserved archaeological wood by means of CT. A key feature of CuTAWAY is the holistic approach to investigating both wood anatomy and conservation methods. This paper aims to review CT methods for the analysis of conserved wooden structures as well as discuss the technical challenges involved in obtaining the first results.

**COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY AND ITS APPLICATION IN
DENDROARCHAEOLOGY****Technical introduction to computed tomography**

CT analyses the 3D structure of wood. In particular, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (Unger et al. 1988, Mori et al. 2019, Capuani et al. 2020),

ter recovery. Here, an overview is given about the use of computed tomography techniques to analyse the structure of conserved wooden artefacts. Besides tree-ring analyses and wood identification, the focus of this investigation is conservation science. In the recently started project CuTAWAY (Conservation and Wood Analyses), a representative scientific collection (KUR Collection) is analysed with computed tomography in order to evaluate the impact on wooden structures of the most common conservation methods.

micro-computed tomography (μ -CT), sub-micro-computed tomography (sub- μ -CT) (Van den Bulcke et al. 2009, Grabner et al. 2009, Bill et al. 2012, Haneca et al. 2012, Stelzner and Million 2015), computed tomography with synchrotron radiation (Dreossi et al. 2009, Mizuno et al. 2010) and neutrons (Osterloh et al. 2008, Mannes 2009) have been used to analyse archaeological wood.

CT is based on the fact that the properties of the radiation used change after penetrating an object. The change in radiation (attenuation) is detected by a suitable detector. Depending on the technology, either the object is rotated around its own axis between the radiation source and detector or the radiation source and detector rotate around the object. Projections are recorded for each angular position in small steps and virtual cross-sections are calculated from the projection data in a process called reconstruction. The resulting stack of equidistant images is a volume stack of the object. For the reconstruction, a few hundred projections are combined to establish the distribution of the attenuation in the investigated material, and a three-dimensional matrix of the attenuation coefficients is calculated using a reconstruction algorithm (Feldkamp et al. 1984). MRI is suitable for examining wood that is still wet but not for wood that has already been conserved and dried (Mori et al. 2019). Due to the limited access to CT with synchrotron radiation (ring accelerators) and neutrons (nuclear reactors), their measurement time is limited. The widely available industrial μ -CT and sub- μ -CT are therefore suitable for larger studies. The success of archaeological wood analysis with μ -CT and sub- μ -CT is critically influenced by the scan resolution, which in turn is determined by the system used for the analysis as well as the sample size (Stelzner and Million 2015). Apart from the effective size of the focal spot (S) and the detector resolution ($P = \text{pixel size}$), scan resolution ($V = \text{voxel size}$) is influenced by object diameter (d):

$$V = \frac{P}{M} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{M}\right)S \quad (1)$$

The relevant magnification (M) in Equation 1 (Mouze 1996) is determined by the distance of the X-ray source ($FOD = \text{focus to object distance}$) and the detector ($FDD = \text{focus to detector distance}$):

$$M = \frac{FDD}{FOD} \quad (2)$$

The distances between object, detector and X-ray source are dependent on object diameter (d), if the object is turned through 360° during the scan. If it is intended to capture the entire object, the maximal achievable magnification (M_{\max}) is furthermore determined by the relation between object diameter (d) and detector width (D):

$$M_{\max} = \frac{D}{d} \quad (3)$$

The resolution of the sub- μ -CT is superior to the μ -CT in terms of recognising details, the sharpness of the image and the geometric resolution and contrast due to the smaller focal spot size. However, the sub- μ -CT has a poorer signal-to-noise ratio due to the limited radiation intensity and is only suitable for smaller samples (Kastner et al. 2010).

Tree-ring analyses

Dendrochronological analysis relies on the fact that the growth of a tree is marked by the development of annual tree rings and their width is to a great extent influenced by the regional climate so that the mean patterns in a certain climate region can be cross-dated (Schweingruber 2001, Billamboz 2009). When the outermost tree ring under the bark (waney edge) has been preserved, both the felling date and the felling season can be determined (Sass-Klaassen et al. 2008). In general, the artefact has to be cut or drilled. The width of the tree rings is usually measured on the cross-section with an accuracy of 1/100 mm (Westphal and Heußner 2016).

This conventional approach is not appropriate for unique archaeological objects. The first attempts to use CT images for non-destructive dating of wood samples were carried out in the 1980s (Onoe et al. 1984). However, the resolution of the medical CT scanner employed for the analysis of the archaeological wood was insufficient for the detection of growth rings with widths below 1 mm (Reimers et al. 1989, Preuss et al. 1991) and 0.4 mm (Klein and Vogel 1994). Even current medical CT scanners cannot provide a sufficient resolution for non-destructive dating (Rigon et al. 2010, Bill et al. 2012). Non-destructive analysis and successful dating of wood samples only became feasible with the development of industrial μ -CT (Okochi et al. 2007). For instance, the oak figures from Fellbach-Schmidlen were dated to 127 BC (\pm 10 years) (Keefer et al. 2006) and the oak figure from Eschenz to 9 BC (\pm 10 years) (Belz et al. 2008) based on industrial μ -CT images. Grabner et al. (2007 and 2009) managed to date archaeological objects from Hallstatt, which had been preserved under conditions encountered in a salt mine. Furthermore, the dendrochronology of wood in blocks of soil was explored with μ -CT (Stelzner and Million 2015), enabling the dating of fragments of oak (AD 500: no waney edge).

Kastner et al. (2010), Grabner et al. (2007 and 2009), Bill et al. (2012) and Stelzner and Million (2015) have all reported on the limits of the measurability of year ring widths, as the image resolution depends on the object size. Grabner et al. (2009) managed to achieve measurements of ring widths down to 0.12 mm. CT with cold neutrons was also tested on samples from Hallstatt objects using a micro-tomography setup. It was possible to resolve ring widths down to 0.15 mm (Mannes 2009). Higher resolution can be reached in X-ray computed tomography with synchrotron radiation – for example in dendrochronological dating of historical violins (Rigon et al. 2010).

A large-scale study of more than 90 oak objects confirmed the potential of μ -CT for non-destructive dendrochronological analysis, with only six objects remaining undated (Bill et al. 2012). However, an important factor affecting the validity of the results is how the samples have been treated. The waterlogged finds examined by Bill et al. (2012) had been air-dried because the measurements of the water-saturated timbers and of the samples impregnated with high-molecular polyethylene glycol (PEG) did not produce sufficient contrast for a determination of tree-ring widths. Apart from the figure from Eschenz (alcohol-ether-resin method) and the

Figure 1. Oak sample, non-degraded (0.43 g/ccm³), conserved with 20% PEG 2000 before freeze-drying

Figure 2. Oak sample, non-degraded (0.44 g/ccm³), conserved with 20% PEG 2000 and 20% PEG 400 before freeze-drying

Figure 3. Oak sample, very degraded (0.11 g/ccm³), conserved with 20% PEG 2000 before freeze-drying

Figure 4. Oak sample, very degraded (0.12 g/ccm³) conserved with 20% PEG 2000 and 20% PEG 400 before freeze-drying

figures from Fellbach-Schmidlen, which had been conserved with Lyofix, no conserved objects have been dated so far by CT and, therefore, Bill et al. (2012) recommend that further experiments should be carried out with CT and conserved wood for dendrochronology.

In μ -CT measurements of a Neolithic wooden wheel made of maple (*Acer* sp., diffuse porous), Wiesner et al. (2016) found cell collapse after impregnation with 40% PEG 2000 and freeze-drying. In this example, the identification of a suitable conservation agent for wet wood from archaeological contexts, which does not interfere with non-destructive dendrochronology (Bill et al. 2012), turned out to be very challenging: μ -CT measurements were performed before conservation in wet condition and after conservation. When wet, the structure of the tree rings was not visible. After conservation, the contrast improved in selected central areas where no conserving agent was present after freeze-drying and the wood structure had collapsed. The residual structure was bulked by the conservation agent so that no structural details were visible. Therefore, neither dating based on CT data nor conventional methods were successful. The wheel could only be dated indirectly to 2900–2897 BC based on conventional wane edge dates from beech planks recovered from the same archaeological context.

In contrast, the annual rings of oak samples (ring porous) that had been conserved with 20% PEG 2000 and freeze-drying were visible (see Figures 1 and 2). The influence of the concentration of the conservation agent and the condition of the wood seems apparent (see Figures 3 and 4; Stelzner 2017).

Identification of the wood genus

Wood identification is usually carried out under the microscope by determining the characteristic anatomic features in three different directions. With CT, a high resolution is necessary for genus identification, which can be reached with synchrotron radiation (Dreossi et al. 2009, Mizuno et al. 2010). For small samples, sub- μ -CT is suitable for wood species identification (Grabner et al. 2009, Van den Bulcke et al. 2009, Haneca et al. 2012). Stelzner and Million (2015) analysed mineralised wood on iron objects with sub- μ -CT and managed to identify beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) fragments from the wooden grip of an early medieval sword. Furthermore, with μ -CT, the identification of the genus (oak) was possible on wood fragments in a block of soil.

Evaluation of conservation methods

CT can be a useful tool to analyse the condition of wood. Depending on the source, both waterlogged and dry objects can be analysed with moderate or high resolution. CT has been used to evaluate the conservation process for archaeological wood, for example to analyse the diffusion of sucrose in wet archaeological wood where the water content was detected by MRI and X-ray CT (Unger et al. 1988). In addition, the distribution and adsorption of sucrose was detected using medical CT during and after impregnation. These experiments helped to elucidate that the diffusion of sucrose takes place in a longitudinal direction (Potthast 1995).

CT with neutrons was used to analyse the distribution of PEG 1500 by calculating the different attenuation of wood and the conserving agent (Demoulin et al. 2015). Moreover, it was used to identify alum in the wooden structure from the Oseberg finds (Braovac and Kutzke 2012).

Bugani et al. (2008) detected the absorption of PEG 1500, PPG 425 and polyisoeugenol in wooden cells with μ -CT and synchrotron-based CT. By means of tomographic imaging, the distribution of consolidants inside the degraded wood matrix could be visualised. With synchrotron-based CT, Christensen (2013) detected alum at different densities in wooden finds from Oseberg and an uneven distribution of phenol formaldehyde within the retreated wood. Dependent on the concentration of phenol formaldehyde, the blockage of pores and vessels was documented (Christensen 2013, Christensen et al. 2014). Also, synchrotron-based CT was used to analyse the structure of Kauramin- and PEG 3000-retreated finds from Oseberg. Full penetration of the conservation agents into the wood samples as well as an open and porous structure of the conserved wood was verified. The wooden cells were coated with PEG 3000 (Braovac et al. in press).

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

This review shows that a systematic observation of the application and development of imaging techniques for conserved objects with a non-destructive method such as μ -CT is of major interest and importance. In 2019, work began on the binational research project CuTAWAY, the aim of which is to provide new insights into already conserved archaeological wood by means of CT. A key feature of CuTAWAY is the transdisciplinary approach to investigate CT for dendroarchaeology with a focus on the wood structure (anatomy, tree-ring analyses) as well as the condition and the impact of the conservation method.

Potential and technical challenges

A major challenge in X-ray tomographic imaging of conserved archaeological wood is the minor difference in X-ray absorption between the different constituents. For small samples, this problem is addressed by imaging with low-energy photons. For larger samples, high X-ray photon energies (above 50 keV) are required to penetrate the sample, for which the contrast is very limited (Chantler 1995). The contrast in tomographic images can be increased by three different approaches. First, the noise in the tomographic images can be reduced by careful optimisation of the acquisition protocol (Jerjen et al. 2015). Second, this optimisation can be combined with image processing techniques to further reduce the influence of noise and scattered radiation (Schuetz et al. 2013 and 2014) as well as reduce the contrast limiting contribution of strong absorbing inclusions such as metallic particles. A third strategy is to image material properties complementary to the X-ray attenuation, such as small angle scattering due to a change in the refractive index. These so-called phase-contrast imaging techniques are an ideal tool to detect small differences in the refractive index as well as tiny interfaces and cracks in a sample. The list of successful applications comprises not only cellular materials such as wood (Derome et al. 2011) but also concrete (Yang et al. 2014), bricks (Jerjen et al. 2010) and fibre

reinforced materials (Revol et al. 2013). Due to the high sensitivity of interfaces between materials, phase-contrast imaging is suitable to investigate the distribution of sub-pixel sized inclusions in macroscopic samples (Revol et al. 2011).

The archaeological sample material

In the 1970s, the most important known conservation methods for wet archaeological wooden finds were compared (Braker and Bill 1979). This experiment was repeated in 2009 by the Römisch–Germanisches Zentralmuseum (RGZM) and the Archäologischen Staatssammlung in München (ASS). This three-year project (the KUR Project) was funded by the Federal Cultural Foundation and the Cultural Foundation of German States and carried out in collaboration with international partners. In this study, 31 wooden samples preserved in waterlogged environments were cut into pieces of a minimum size of $10 \times 6 \times 6 \text{ cm}^3$. About 800 samples were photo-documented, the wooden specimens were analysed and the state of preservation was assessed by the water content (U_{max}). Then, the samples were conserved by experts at different institutions using their standard methods (Table 1).

Table 1. Overview of conservation methods and participants in the KUR Project

Conservation method	Participating institution
Kauramin 800	Römisch Germanisches Zentralmuseum Mainz, Germany
Saccharose	Sächsische Landesamt für Archäologie Dresden, Germany
Lactitol/Trehalose	Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege Zossen, Germany
Silicon oil	Texas University, Texas, USA
Alcohol-Ether-Resin	Swiss National Museum, Zürich, Switzerland
One-step polyethylene glycol (PEG) and freeze-drying	National Museum of Denmark, Copenhagen, Denmark
Two-step polyethylene glycol (PEG) and freeze-drying (PEGcon)	Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege Zossen, Germany
Three-step polyethylene glycol (PEG) and freeze-drying	Archäologische Staatssammlung, München, Germany

The success of the different methods was determined by manually calculating the anti-shrink efficiency and by comparing the volume of the samples' surface before and after conservation by means of a 3D scanner (Wittkoepper et al. 2016). The results are publicly available on the online database (<https://www.rgzm.de/kur>, 01.10.2019). This comprehensive and systematic collection of samples provides a unique chance to compare the structural differences of the conserved wood.

Further work

A selection of the collected samples from the KUR Project will be performed. These samples will be analysed at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts with an industrial μ -CT system (diondo d2). Therefore, an optimised setup and acquisition protocol for the CT measurements will be developed for conserved wood. New artefact reduction and reconstruction algorithms, as well as quantitative image analysis, will be developed and (environmental) scattering reduced. Alongside instrumentation and

acquisition protocols, new iterative reconstruction algorithms will have to be developed (Yu et al. 2014). In the next step, more challenging wood species with lower contrast will be analysed. Also, methods like neutron and phase-contrast micro-computed tomography will be compared to μ -CT. In order to analyse the structure of wet wood, MRI will be carried out. In parallel, a methodological approach will be undertaken to relate CT and optical scans.

In order to improve the shrinkage measurements for waterlogged wood, both CT measurements and optical 3D scans will be compared. By extending conventional 3D scans, CT images also elucidate cracks and signs of structural collapse. A comparative study of the inner structure of the wood conserved with the most common methods, as well as an optimised method to evaluate the volume of the samples taking internal cracks into consideration, will be used.

In order to archive a higher resolution, subsamples will be taken from the KUR samples. Here, a detailed analysis of the wood anatomy and the conservation agent permeability will be carried out to arrive at conclusions about the success of the conservation treatments. In parallel, microscopic analyses will be performed to compare and interpret the information gained. Additionally, long-term stability will be analysed and evaluated by simulated ageing tests on conserved wooden samples. The information will be presented and stored on a database as open source (<https://www.rgzm.de/kur>).

CONCLUSION

In order to exploit both data provided by the wooden structure as dendrochronology and conservation methods, non-destructive analysis techniques for conserved archaeological artefacts are necessary. CT is a very promising technique as preliminary results have shown. The CT measurements refer to the condition of the wooden structure. Cracks, collapse and other structural damage is visible, which enables an improvement in shrinkage measurements and therefore an improvement in the evaluation of the dimensional stability. However, the conservation agent and the wooden structure have a similar attenuation factor, which prevents a detailed analysis of the wooden texture. Therefore, the implementation of new, non-destructive techniques is necessary to analyse both the wooden structure and the effect of the conservation treatments in detail. Further work will focus on the CT analysis of samples conserved using the standard conservation treatments collected in the RGZM during the framework programme funded by KUR (KUR Collection). This holistic approach will guarantee that archaeological wooden artefacts can be better studied and conserved for future generations.

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REFERENCES

- Belz, E., H. Brem, A. Hasenfratz, R. Kauermann, U. Leuzinger, C. Müller, R. Schweichel, and D. Steiner. 2008. Neue Erkenntnisse zur Datierung der Holzstatue von Eschenz. *Jahrbuch Archäologie Schweiz* 91: 134–40.
- Bill, J., K.S. Dalen, A. Daly, and Ø. Johnsen. 2012. DendroCT – Dendrochronology without damage. *Dendrochronologia* 30: 223–30. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dendro.2011.11.002>
- Billamboz, A. 2009. Jahrringuntersuchungen in der Siedlung Forschner und weiteren bronze- und eisenzeitlichen Feuchtbodensiedlungen Südwestdeutschlands. Aussagen der angewandten Dendrochronologie in der Feuchtbodenarchäologie. In *Siedlungsarchäologie im Alpenvorland XI*, ed. Landesamt für Denkmalpflege im Regierungspräsidium Stuttgart, *Forschungen und Berichte zur Ur- und Frühgeschichte in Baden-Württemberg* 113: 339–556. Stuttgart: Konrad Theiss.
- Braker, O.U. and J. Bill. 1979. Zum derzeitigen Stand der Naßholzkonservierung. *Zeitschrift für Schweizerische Archäologie und Kunstgeschichte* 36: 97–145.
- Braovac, S. and H. Kutzke. 2012. Past conservation treatments and their consequences: The Oseberg find as a case study. In *Proceedings of the 11th ICOM-CC Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference, Greenville (US), 24–28 May 2010*, eds. K. Strætkvern and E. Williams, 481–95. Lulu.com: International Council of Museums.
- Braovac, S., M. Saliæt, and M. Wittkoepper. In press. Retreatment testing of alum-treated woods from the Oseberg collection – Results from first trials. In *Proceedings of the 14th ICOM-CC Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference, Portsmouth (UK), 20–24 May 2019*.
- Bugani, S., P. Cloetens, M.P. Colombini, G. Giachi, K. Janssens, F. Modugno, L. Morselli, and E. van de Casteele. 2008. Evaluation of conservation treatments for archaeological waterlogged wooden artifacts. In *Art2008: 9th International Conference on NDT of Art, Jerusalem (Israel), 25–30 May 2008*. 6. NDT.net.
- Capuani, S., V. Stagno, M. Missori, L. Sadori, and S. Longo. 2020. High-resolution multiparametric MRI of contemporary and waterlogged archaeological wood. *Magnetic Resonance in Chemistry* 58(9): 860–9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/mrc.5034>
- Chantler, C.T. 1995. Theoretical form factor, attenuation, and scattering tabulation for $Z=1-92$ from $E=1-10$ eV to $E=0.4-1.0$ MeV. *Journal of Physical and Chemical Reference Data* 24(1): 71–643. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.555974>
- Christensen, M. 2013. Developing new consolidants for archaeological wood. PhD dissertation, University of Oslo, Norway.
- Christensen, M., H. Kutzke, and F.K. Hansen. 2014. Phenol formaldehyde revisited – Novolac resins for the treatment of degraded archaeological wood. *Archaeometry* 57(3): 536–59. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/arcm.12097>
- Demoulin, T., R. Gebhard, and B. Schillinger. 2015. Neutron tomography of archaeological waterlogged wood. *Restaurierung und Archäologie* 8: 27–33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11588/ra.2015.0.37020>
- Derome, D., M. Griffa, M. Koebel, and J. Carmeliet. 2011. Hysteretic swelling of wood at cellular scale probed by phase-contrast X-ray tomography. *Journal of Structural Biology* 173(1): 180–90. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsb.2010.08.011>

Dreossi, D., S. Favretto, M. Fioravanti, L. Mancini, L. Rigon, N. Sodini, N., G. Tromba, and F. Zanini. 2009. Synchrotron radiation micro-tomography: A non-invasive tool for the characterization of archaeological wood. In *Wood Science for Conservation of Cultural Heritage: Proceedings of the International Conference held by COST Action IE0601, Florence (Italy), 8–10 November 2007*, ed. L. Uzielli, 34–9. Florence: Firenze University Press.

Grabner, M., J. Kastner, A. Klein, J. Reschreiter, and D. Salaberger. 2007. Dendrochronologische Datierung von Holzfunden aus Hallstatt mit Hilfe der Röntgen-Computertomographie. In *Interpretierte Eisenzeiten 2. Fallstudien, Methoden, Theorien*, eds R. Karl and J. Leskovar, *Studien zur Kulturgeschichte von Oberösterreich* 19: 99–108.

Grabner, M., D. Salaberger, and T. Okochi. 2009. The need of high resolution μ -X-ray CT in dendrochronology and in wood identification. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Symposium on Image and Signal Processing and Analysis, Salzburg (Austria), 16–18 September 2009*, 349–52. IEEE. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISPA.2009.5297695>

Haneca, K., K. Deforce, M.N. Boone, D. van Loo, M. Dierick, J. van Acker, and J. van den Bulcke. 2012. X-ray sub-micron tomography as a tool for the study of archaeological wood preserved through the corrosion of metal objects. *Archaeometry* 54(5): 893–905. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4754.2011.00640>

Jerjen, I., V. Revol, C. Kottler, T. Luethi, U. Sennhauser, R. Kaufmann, and C. Urban. 2010. Differentielle Phasenkonstrasttomographie: Eine vielversprechende Methode für die zerstörungsfreie Prüfung. In *Proceedings of the 3rd Industrielle Computertomografie Fachtagung, Wels (Austria), 27–29 September 2010*, ed. J. Kastner, 271–6. Aachen: Shaker.

Jerjen, I., L.D. Poulidakos, M. Plamondon, P. Schuetz, T. Luethi, and A. Flisch. 2015. Drying of porous asphalt concrete investigated by X-ray computed tomography. *Physics Procedia* 69: 451–6. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phpro.2015.07.063>

Kastner, J., B. Harrer, G. Requena, and O. Brunke. 2010. A comparative study of high-resolution cone beam X-ray tomography and synchrotron tomography applied to Fe- and Al-alloys. *NDT & E International* 43(7): 599–605. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ndteint.2010.06.004>

Keefer, E., I. Pfeifer-Schällner, C. Sauerwein, and H. Wälischmiller. 2006. Voxel and STL-data in service of archaeology – Digital Celts. In *Proceedings of the 9th European Conference on Non-Destructive Testing, Berlin (Germany), 25–29 September 2006*, eds J. Völker and R. Link. Berlin: Tu.3.2.4.

Klein, P. and H. Vogel. 1994. Computertomografie – Eine Hilfe für Dendrochronologie und Holzartenbestimmung? In *4th International Conference on Non-Destructive Testing of Works of Art, Berlin (Germany), 3–8 October 1994*, *Berichtsband* 45(2), 85–91. Berlin: DGZfP.

Mannes, D. 2009. Non-destructive testing of wood by means of neutron imaging in comparison with similar methods. PhD dissertation, ETH Zurich, Switzerland.

Mizuno, S., R. Torizu, and J. Sugiyama. 2010. Wood identification of a wooden mask using synchrotron X-ray microtomography. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 37(11): 2842–5. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2010.06.022>

Mori, M., S. Kuhara, K. Kobayashi, S. Suzuki, M. Yamada, and A. Senoo. 2019. Non-destructive tree-ring measurements using a clinical 3T-MRI for archaeology. *Dendrochronologia* 57: 125630. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dendro.2019.125630>

Mouze, D. 1996. X-ray microradiography. In *Handbook of microscopy: Applications in materials science, solid-state physics, and chemistry. Methods II*, eds S. Amelinckx, D. Van Dyck, J. Van Landuyt, and G. Van Tendeloo, 130–47. Weinheim: VCH.

Okochi, T., H. Fujii, and T. Mitsutani. 2007. Nondestructive tree-ring measurements for Japanese oak and Japanese beech using micro-focus X-ray computed tomography. *Dendrochronologia* 24: 155–64. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dendro.2006.10.010>

Onoe, M., J.W. Tsao, H. Yamada, H. Nakamura, J. Kogure, H. Kawamura, and M. Yoshimatsu. 1984. Computed tomography for measuring the annual rings of a live tree. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research* 221(1): 213–20. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/PROC.1983.12691>

Osterloh, K., C. Raedel, U. Zscherpel, D. Meinel, U. Ewert, T. Buecherl, and A. Hasenstab. 2008. Fast neutron radiography and tomography of wood. *Insight* 50(6): 307–11. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1784/insi.2008.50.6.307>

- Potthast, I. 1995. Computertomographische Untersuchungen zum Eindringverhalten von Saccharose-Lösung bei der Stabilisierung von archäologischem Nassholz. Diploma thesis, Staatliche Akademie der Bildenden Künste Stuttgart, Germany.
- Preuss, P., K. Christensen, and K. Peters. K. 1991. The use of computer-tomographical X-ray scanning in dendrochronology. *Norwegian Archaeological Review* 24(2): 123–30. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00293652.1991.9965538>
- Reimers, P., J. Riederer, J. Goebels, and A. Kettschau. 1989. Dendrochronology by means of X-ray computed tomography (CT). In *Archaeometry: Proceedings of the 25th International Symposium, Athens (Greece), 19–23 May 1986*, ed. Y. Maniatis, 121–5. Amsterdam: Elsevier Science.
- Revol, V., I. Jerjen, C. Kottler, P. Schuetz, R. Kaufmann, T. Lüthi, U. Sennhauser, U. Straumann, and C. Urban. 2011. Sub-pixel porosity revealed by X-ray scatter dark field imaging. *Journal of Applied Physics* 110(4): 044912. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3624592>
- Revol, V., B. Plank, R. Kaufmann, J. Kastner, C. Kottler, and A. Neels. 2013. Laminate fibre structure characterisation of carbon fibre-reinforced polymers by X-ray scatter dark field imaging with a grating interferometer. *NDT & E International* 58: 64–71.
- Rigon, L., E. Vallazza, F. Arfelli, R. Longo, D. Dreossi, A. Bergamaschi, B. Schmitt, R. Chen, M.A. Cova, R. Perabò, M. Fioravanti, L. Mancini, R.H. Menk, G. Sodini, G. Tromba, and F. Zanini. 2010. Synchrotron-radiation microtomography for the non-destructive structural evaluation of bowed stringed instruments. *E-Preservation Science* 7: 71–7.
- Sass-Klaassen, U., T. Vernimmen, and C. Baittinger. 2008. Dendrochronological dating and provenancing of timbers used as foundation piles under historic buildings in The Netherlands. *International Biodeterioration and Biodegradation* 61: 96–105. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibiod.2007.07.013>
- Schuetz, P., A. Miceli, I. Jerjen, A. Flisch, R. Brönnimann, and U. Sennhauser. 2013. Reducing environmental scattering in industrial computed tomography by system redesign. *NDT & E International* 28: 36–42.
- Schuetz, P., I. Jerjen, J. Hofmann, M. Plamondon, A. Flisch, and U. Sennhauser. 2014. Correction algorithm for environmental scattering in industrial computed tomography. *NDT & E International* 64: 59–64.
- Schweingruber, F.H. 2001. *Dendroökologische Holz Anatomie. Anatomische Grundlagen der Dendrochronologie*, ed. Eidgenössische Forschungsanstalt WSL. Bern: Paul Haupt.
- Stelzner, I. 2017. Bestimmung prozessrelevanter Eigenschaften für die Gefriertrocknung in der Nassholzkonservierung. PhD dissertation, Staatliche Akademie der Bildenden Künste Stuttgart, Germany.
- Stelzner, J. and S. Million. 2015. X-ray computed tomography for anatomical and dendrochronological analysis of archaeological wood. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 55: 188–96. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2014.12.015>
- Stelzner, J. 2020. Die Computertomographie als Untersuchungs- und Dokumentationsmethode zur Bearbeitung frühmittelalterlicher Fundkomplexe. In *Lauchheim I*, eds. D. Krausse, S. Brather, J. Scheschkewitz, N. Ebinger, and I. Stork, *Forschungen und Berichte zur Archäologie in Baden- Württemberg* 8: 11–133.
- Unger, A., J. Planitzer, and A. Morgós. 1988. Röntgencomputer- und Magnetresonanztomographie zur Charakterisierung von archäologischem Naßholz. *Holztechnologie* 29: 249–50.
- Van den Bulcke, J., M. Boone, J. van Acker, M. Stevens, and L. van Hoorebeke. 2009. X-ray tomography as a tool for detailed anatomical analysis. *Annals of Forest Science* 66: 508. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/forest/2009033>
- Westphal, T. and K.U. Heußner. 2016. *Kleiner Leitfaden für den Umgang mit Holz für dendrochronologische Altersbestimmung*. München: Dr. Friedrich Pfeil.
- Wiesner, I., J. Stelzner, S. Million, K. Kuhnt, and K. Bott. 2016. The first wheels go round again. In *Proceedings of the 12th ICOM-CC Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference, Greenville (US), 14–17 May 2010*, eds. T. Grant and C. Cook, 197–8. Lulu.com: International Council of Museums.

Wittkoepper, M., W. Muskalla, S. Brather, A. LeBoedec-Moesgard, S. Gebhard, S. Klönk, C. André, K. Schmidt-Ott, and W. Smith. 2016. The KUR (conservation and restoration) Project. A comparison of different methods to preserve waterlogged wood. In *Proceedings of the 12th ICOM-CC Group on Wet Organic Archaeological Materials Conference, Greenville (US), 14–17 May 2010*, eds. T. Grant and C. Cook, 134–143. Lulu.com: International Council of Museums.

Yang, F., F. Prade, M. Griffa, I. Jerjen, C. di Bella, J. Herzen, A. Sarapata, F. Pfeiffer, and P. Lura. 2014. Dark-field X-ray imaging of unsaturated water transport in porous materials. *Applied Physics Letters* 105: 154105. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4898783>

Yu, L., P. Schuetz, A. Flisch, and U. Sennhauser. 2014. Exploring the limits of limited-angle computed tomography complemented with surface data. In *Proceedings of the 11th European Conference on Non-Destructive Testing, Prague (Czech Republic), 6–10 October 2014*, ed. P. Mazal. Bad Breisig: Brno University of Technology.

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